

United States Department of the Interior

In Reply Refer to:
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FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
Sacramento Fish and Wildlife Office
2800 Cottage Way, Suite W-2605
Sacramento, California 95825-1846

SEP 21 2018

Ms. Jo Ann Cullom
California Department of Transportation
Environmental Division, MS-8E
111 Grand Avenue
Oakland, California 94612

Subject: Formal Consultation on the Interstate 580 Stege Drain Bridge Rehabilitation Project, Contra Costa County, California (Caltrans EA 2J720)

Dear Ms. Cullom:

This letter is in response to the California Department of Transportation's (Caltrans) May 3, 2018 request to initiate formal consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) on the proposed Interstate 580 (I-580) Stege Drain Bridge Rehabilitation Project in Contra Costa County, California. Your request was received by the Service on May 3, 2018. At issue are the proposed project's effects on the federally threatened California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) and endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*). Critical habitat has not been designated for the California clapper rail or salt marsh harvest mouse. This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. § 1531 et seq.) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR 402). Due to recent taxonomic changes, the California clapper rail is now referred to in scientific literature as the California Ridgway's rail (*Rallus obsoletus obsoletus*), but for the purposes of this document we will use the original name, as that remains the listed entity under the Act.

Fixing America's Surface Transportation Act (FAST Act) was signed into law on December 4, 2015. Providing funding from 2016 to 2020, the FAST Act includes provisions to promote streamlined and accelerated project delivery. Caltrans is approved to participate in the FAST Act project delivery program through the National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA) Assignment Memorandum of Understanding (MOU). The MOU allows Caltrans to assume the Federal Highway Administration's (FHWA) responsibilities under NEPA as well as FHWA's consultation and coordination responsibilities under federal environmental laws for most highway projects in California. Caltrans is exercising this authority as the federal nexus for section 7 consultation on this project.

The federal action we are consulting on includes the proposed replacement of the existing Stege Drain Bridge (Bridge No. 28-0091) over Baxter Creek at post mile 1.17 on I-580 in the City of Richmond, California. Caltrans submitted a Biological Assessment (BA) for our review and requested concurrence with the findings presented therein. These findings conclude that the proposed project may affect, and is likely to adversely affect the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse.

In considering your request, we based our evaluation on the following: (1) the Service's January 25, 2018 visit to the proposed project site; (2) Caltrans' May 3, 2018 request for consultation along with an accompanying April 2018, BA; (3) Caltrans' July 19 2018 response to the Service's June 29, 2018 electronic mail (e-mail) message; (4) correspondence outlined in the *Consultation History*; and (5) other information available to the Service.

The remainder of this document provides our biological opinion on the effects of the proposed project on the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse.

Consultation History

January 25, 2018	The Service visited the proposed project site with Caltrans to become acquainted with the project description and offer technical assistance.
May 3, 2018	The Service received a May 3, 2018, request for consultation from Caltrans along with an April 2018 BA.
June 29, 2018	The Service sent Caltrans an e-mail message requesting additional information needed to complete the requested consultation. The message was the equivalent of a 30-day letter.
July 19, 2018	Caltrans provided additional project information in response to the June 29, 2018 information request sent by the Service.
August 7, 2018	Caltrans provided the Service with updated project information via an e-mail message.
August 31, 2018	Caltrans provided the Service with requested project information via an e-mail message.

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

Description of the Action

Caltrans proposes to replace the existing I-580 bridge over Baxter Creek in the City of Richmond. The bridge is located at Post Mile 1.17 and is referred to as the Stege Drain Bridge. The existing bridge is structurally deficient and will be replaced in-kind with a similar slab structure. The existing bridge is approximately 139-feet wide and includes three lanes of traffic in either direction, standard road shoulders, a concrete median, and a southbound on-ramp lane which merges onto I-580 immediately south of the bridge. The bridge is flanked by the Bayview Avenue Overpass and interchange to the north, a parallel northbound Bayview Avenue off-ramp and a railroad to the east, and tidally influenced wetlands and the San Francisco Bay to the west.

In order to maintain through traffic, the bridge will be dismantled and rebuilt in four individual segments. Pavement will be removed up to 12 feet beyond the bridge abutments to the north and south. The existing abutments will remain in place and no alteration of Baxter Creek will occur. As a result, no water diversion will be needed and a debris containment system will be installed below the existing bridge deck to prohibit materials from falling into the creek. Water may intrude into the excavation behind the abutments, where it will be pumped out and contained in Baker tanks for treatment and discharge offsite.

Piles will be percussively driven with an impact hammer to build the new under-pavement support grade beams behind the abutments. Each of the 36 piles is anticipated to take approximately 475 blows (10.5 minutes active driving) to complete. The area behind the newly constructed grade beams will be backfilled with engineered fill and compacted before pavement is laid on top.

The new bridge deck will be installed following the abutment work associated with each of the four sequencing stages. The completed bridge will include a concrete median barrier and guard rails. Three new light emitting diode street lights will be installed at the merge of I-580 and the southbound Bayview Avenue on-ramp.

The bridge rehabilitation will require areas for temporary construction access, installation of stream protection measures, temporary realignment of the Bayview Avenue southbound on-ramp, and the staging of materials/vehicles. The Bayview Avenue interchange cloverleaf north of the bridge will be used for staging and stockpiling. To access this area, a temporary crossing of an engineered channel will be required. The channel crossing will be constructed of a large corrugated pipe and clean river rock. This temporary channel crossing will be completely removed at the end of the project. Areas beyond the east and west shoulders of I-580 will be used as staging and may need to be leveled and stabilized for large equipment. All disturbed areas will be recontoured to preexisting conditions and revegetated with an assemblage of native plant species.

Construction is expected to begin in 2021 and take two years to complete. Bridge demolition and building work over Baxter Creek will be limited to a period between July 15 and October 15. Construction beyond the abutments will occur between July 15 and January 31.

Conservation Measures

Caltrans proposes to reduce adverse effects to the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse by implementing the following measures:

1. **Permits.** Caltrans will include a copy of the all relevant permits within the construction bid package of the proposed project. The Resident Engineer or their designee will be responsible for implementing the terms and conditions of all project regulatory permits.
2. **Approval of Biological Monitors.** Caltrans will submit the names and qualifications of proposed biological monitor(s) for Service and California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW) approval prior to initiating construction activities for the proposed project. Only Agency-Approved Biological Monitors will implement the monitoring duties outlined in the Biological Opinion including delivery of the Worker Environmental Awareness Training Program.
3. **Biological Monitoring.** An Agency-Approved Biological Monitor will be present to monitor for California clapper rail, salt marsh harvest mouse, and other special-status species prior to and during construction activities within and adjacent to suitable habitat. The Agency-Approved Biological Monitor will have the authority to stop work if deemed necessary for any reason to protect the species. If a listed species is observed in the work area, work will be stopped immediately by the Agency-Approved Biological Monitor until the individual(s) leaves the work area on its own volition. If the individual(s) does not leave the work area, work will not be reinitiated until after the Service has been contacted and a decision reached on how construction activities could proceed. The project resident engineer or construction inspector will consult with the Agency-Approved Biological Monitor on how to proceed. The Agency-Approved Biological Monitor will also inspect the wildlife exclusion fence (WEF) along the margins of project work areas.

4. **Listed Species in Construction Zones.** The resident engineer will immediately contact the Agency-Approved Biological Monitor and the Service/CDFW in the event that a California clapper rail, salt marsh harvest mouse, or other listed species gains access to a construction zone. To avoid a take, the resident engineer will suspend construction activities within a 50-foot radius of the animal until the animal leaves the site voluntarily or is removed by the Agency-Approved Biological Monitor to a release site using Service and CDFW-approved handling techniques.
5. **Worker Environmental Training.** All construction personnel will attend a mandatory environmental education program delivered by an Agency-Approved Biological Monitor prior to working in the Action Area. The program will focus on the conservation measures that are relevant to employee's personal responsibility and will include an explanation as how to best avoid take of the California clapper rail or salt marsh harvest mouse. Distributed materials will include a pamphlet with distinguishing photographs of sensitive species, species' habitat requirements, compliance reminders, and relevant contact information. Documentation of the training, including sign-in sheets, would be kept on file and would be available on request.
6. **Pre-Construction Surveys Prior to Initial Ground Disturbance.** Pre-construction surveys will be conducted by an Agency-Approved Biological Monitor in areas of potential habitat for California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse immediately prior to any ground disturbance, including staging of equipment or materials. These surveys will consist of walking surveys of the project limits and accessible adjacent areas within at least 50 feet of the project limits to determine presence of the species. If a listed species is observed, all project work within the vicinity will cease and the Service and CDFW will be contacted to determine how to proceed. Under no circumstances will the capture, handling, or relocation of a California clapper rail or salt marsh harvest mouse occur unless expressly authorized by the Service and CDFW.
7. **Wildlife Exclusion Fencing.** Prior to the start of construction, a temporary salt marsh harvest mouse-proof WEF will be erected to discourage the movement of salt marsh harvest mice into the construction zone. The WEF will consist of corrugated metal or plywood fencing a minimum of 1 foot higher than adjacent vegetation and buried 1 foot deep into the soil to prevent mice from burrowing under them. To ensure proper exclusion, the WEF will terminate at permanent passage barriers (e.g., permanent water, high levee, roadway edge) at both ends.
8. **Major Tides & Construction.** During periods of forecast extreme high (e.g., king) tides, all construction activities will temporarily cease within 50 feet of suitable refugia habitat for the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse. Extreme tides may also occur during weather events (e.g., storms or high winds) that coincide with average high tide events, and those combined phenomena can push water into normally dry zones. Caltrans will use the extreme high tide determinations expressed by Service staff at Don Edwards National Wildlife Refuge as an event greater than 6.5 feet when measured at the Golden Gate tidal station. As a result, impacts to refugia habitat from construction activities will be examined, and construction activities ceased, when tidal events with high tide peaks of greater than 6.5 feet relative to mean low water line measured at the Golden Gate tidal station, combined with strong weather patterns, are forecast. Work also will not occur during the 6 hours before and after a predicted high tide event. Refugia habitat will be defined as high marsh or adjacent transitional areas, including ruderal sites, which are not expected to be inundated during the extreme tidal event.

9. **General Nesting Bird Surveys.** Clearing and grubbing of vegetation will occur outside of the typical nesting bird season (February 1 to September 30), to the degree possible. When it is necessary to conduct clearing during the nesting season, preconstruction surveys will be conducted within the Action Area prior to clearing and grubbing of vegetation. If preconstruction surveys indicate the presence of active nests of bird species protected under the *Migratory Bird Treaty Act*, the Service's Region 8 Migratory Birds Division will be consulted to determine the appropriate buffer area to be established around the nesting site for the duration of the breeding season.
10. **Seasonal Avoidance for California Clapper Rail Nesting.** Construction will be limited from July 15 to January 31.
11. **Non-Disturbance Buffer.** If work is to occur within 300 feet of active raptor nests or 100 feet of active passerine nests, a non-disturbance buffer will be established at a distance sufficient to minimize disturbance based on the nest location, topography, cover, the species' sensitivity to disturbance, and the intensity/type of potential disturbance. Buffer size will be determined in cooperation with an experienced biologist.
12. **Focused Clapper Rail Surveys.** Monthly focused surveys within 700 feet of the project footprint near suitable habitat for active nests, broods, and calling centers will be conducted for California clapper rail during the nesting season from February 1 to September 30. If active nests (nests with eggs or young present), or calling centers are located in the Action Area, all construction activities within the survey areas described above will temporarily cease and the Service will be notified of the observation.
13. **Covering of Trenches & Excavated Holes.** To prevent inadvertent entrapment of salt marsh harvest mice during construction, excavated holes or trenches more than 1 foot deep with walls steeper than 30 degrees will be covered by plywood or similar materials at the close of each working day. Alternatively, an additional 4-foot high vertical barrier, independent of exclusionary fences, will be used to further prevent the inadvertent entrapment of the salt marsh harvest mouse. If it is not feasible to cover an excavation or provide an additional 4-foot high vertical barrier, independent of exclusionary fences, one or more escape ramps constructed of earth fill or wooden planks will be installed. Before such holes or trenches are filled, they will be thoroughly inspected for trapped animals. If at any time a trapped salt marsh harvest mouse is discovered, the Agency-Approved Biological Monitor will immediately place escape ramps or other appropriate structures to allow the animal to escape or the Service will be contacted by telephone for guidance. The Service will be notified of the incident by telephone and e-mail.
14. **Vegetation Removal.** Vegetation removal will be minimized to the maximum extent practicable. Vegetation will be cut above the soil level except in areas that will be excavated. This will increase the probability of plants that reproduce vegetatively to resprout after construction. An Agency-Approved Biological Monitor will be present during all vegetation clearing and grubbing activities within suitable habitat for listed species, and will inspect all areas immediately prior to vegetation clearing. If at any point a California clapper rail, salt marsh harvest mice, or other listed species is discovered during these activities, work will cease until the animal(s) has left the area on its own. To minimize potential impacts to California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mice from construction activities, pickleweed vegetation will be removed using hand-tools only (i.e., motorized tools, including weed whackers, chainsaws, etc., will not be used). All temporarily affected areas with suitable habitat for the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse will be replanted at the

end of construction activity with native vegetation characteristic of that vegetative community.

15. **Debris Containment System.** Prior to the start of construction, a debris containment plan will be submitted to the Service for approval. The debris containment plan will clearly describe acceptable materials and installation methods. The debris containment system will remain in place throughout the duration of the bridge deck removal process and will be regularly inspected and fully maintained at all time. Upon completion of the bridge deck removal and in-stream work, the debris containment system will be completely removed and properly disposed of offsite, the area cleaned of debris and trash, and returned to natural conditions.
16. **Nighttime Construction.** To the extent practicable, nighttime construction will be **minimized**.
17. **Artificial Lighting.** Except when necessary for construction, driver, or pedestrian safety, lighting of the proposed Action Area by artificial lighting during nighttime hours will be **minimized** to the maximum extent practicable. Construction personnel will turn portable tower lights on no more than 30 minutes before the beginning of civil twilight, and off no more than 30 minutes after the end of civil sunrise. Portable tower lights will have directional shields attached to them, and personnel will only direct lights downward and toward active construction and staging areas. Lighting per portable tower light will not exceed 2,000 lumens. To the extent practicable, personnel will only use enough coverage to light the travel way, median, and staging areas.
18. **Vehicle Use.** Vehicle use near suitable habitat for the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse will be **minimized** to the maximum extent practicable. Vehicles will remain on paved roads to the maximum extent practicable, and speeds will be limited to 10 miles per hour when off the pavement.
19. **Dust Control.** Dust control measures will consist of regular truck watering of construction access areas and disturbed soil areas with the use of organic soil stabilizers to **minimize** airborne dust and soil particles generated from graded areas. Regular truck watering will be a requirement of the construction contract. In addition, for disturbed soil areas, an organic tackifier to control dust emissions blowing off of the right of way or out of the construction area during construction will be included in the contract special provisions. Watering guidelines for dewatering will be established to avoid any excessive run-off that may flow into contiguous areas. Any material stockpiles will be watered, sprayed with tackifier, or covered, to **minimize** dust production and wind erosion.
20. **Rain Events.** The Agency-Approved Biological Monitor will determine which construction activities may need to be halted within 24 hours of a 0.1-inch rain event, or when there is a forecast of 40 percent or more chance of precipitation. If, by 2 p.m., rain is forecast for the remainder of the day or subsequent night with a 70 percent or greater probability of rain (based on the nearest National Weather Service forecast, available at <http://forecast.weather.gov>), work may be postponed until 24 hours have passed between the last rain event and the start of work.
21. **Trash.** All food-related trash items such as wrappers, cans, bottles, and food scraps will be disposed of in closed containers and removed regularly from the work area.

22. **Firearms.** No firearms will be allowed in the Action Area except for those carried by authorized security personnel, or local, state, or federal law enforcement officials.
23. **Pets.** To prevent harassment, injury, or mortality of sensitive species, no pets will be permitted in the Action Area.
24. **Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plan.** Dedicated fueling and refueling practices will be outlined as part of the Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plan (SWPPP). Dedicated fueling areas will be protected from stormwater run-on and run-off and will be located at least 50 feet from downslope drainage facilities and water courses. Fueling will be performed on level-grade areas. On-site fueling will only be used where it is impractical to send vehicles and equipment off site for fueling. When fueling must occur on site, the contractor will designate an area to be used subject to the approval of the Caltrans resident engineer. Drip pans or absorbent pads will be used during on-site vehicle and equipment fueling. The potential for adverse effects to water quality will be avoided by implementing temporary and permanent BMPs outlined in Section 7-1.01G of the Caltrans' Standard Specifications. Caltrans erosion control BMPs will be used to minimize any wind- or water-related erosion. The State Water Resources Control Board has issued a National Pollution Discharge Elimination System Statewide Storm Water Permit to Caltrans to regulate stormwater and non-stormwater discharges from Caltrans facilities. A SWPPP will be developed for the project, as one is required for all projects that have at least 1.0 acre of soil disturbance. The SWPPP complies with the Caltrans Storm Water Management Plan (SWMP). The SWMP features guidance for Caltrans design staff to include provisions in construction contracts for measures to protect sensitive areas and to prevent and minimize stormwater and non-stormwater discharges.

The SWPPP will reference the Caltrans Construction Site BMPs Manual. This manual is comprehensive and includes many other protective measures and guidance to prevent and minimize pollutant discharges and can be found online at: <http://www.dot.ca.gov/hq/construc/stormwater/manuals.htm>. Protective measures will be included in the contract, including, at a minimum:

- a. No discharge of pollutants from vehicle and equipment cleaning are allowed into storm drains or water courses.
- b. Vehicle and equipment fueling and maintenance operations will be at least 50 feet away from water courses.
- c. Concrete wastes are collected in washouts and water from curing operations is collected and disposed of and not allowed into water courses.
- d. Dust control will be implemented, including use of water trucks and tackifiers to control dust in excavation and fill areas, rocking temporary access road entrances and exits, and covering temporary stockpiles when weather conditions require.
- e. Coir rolls will be installed along or at the base of slopes during construction to capture sediment, and temporary organic hydro-mulching would be applied to all unfinished disturbed and graded areas.
- f. Work areas where temporary disturbance has removed the pre-existing vegetation will be restored and re-seeded with a native seed mix appropriate for the area.

- g. Graded areas will be protected from erosion using a combination of silt fences, fiber rolls along toe of slopes or along edges of designated staging areas, and erosion-control netting (such as jute or coir) as appropriate.
 - h. A *Revegetation Plan* will be prepared for restoration of temporary work areas.
25. **Monofilament Netting.** To prevent listed species from being entangled, trapped, or injured, erosion control materials with plastic monofilament netting will not be used within the Action Area.
26. **Asphalt Waste.** All grindings and asphaltic-concrete waste will be stored within previously disturbed areas absent of habitat and at a minimum of 150 feet from any aquatic habitat, culvert, or drainage feature.
27. **Replanting with Native Species.** All areas that are temporarily affected during construction will be revegetated with native plant species appropriate to the habitat that was disturbed in order to restore habitat values. Invasive, exotic plants will be controlled within the Action Area to the maximum extent practicable, pursuant to *Executive Order 13112* (Invasive Species).
28. **Care of Injured or Dead Species.** Listed species found injured will be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or a wildlife rehabilitation facility. After hours, interim care may be provided by another experienced person, including the Agency-Approved Biological Monitor, until the animal can be delivered to a facility. Dead individuals of any listed species will be preserved by freezing and held in a secure location. The Service will be notified of the discovery of death or injury to a listed species occurring as a result of project-related activities or if observed at the project site. Notification will include the date, time, and location clearly indicated on a quad or other maps at a finer scale, as requested by the Service and any other pertinent information. Dead individual animals will be placed in a zippered plastic storage bag with a piece of paper attached to the outside of the bag stating where and when the animal was found and the name of the person who found it. The bag will be frozen in a freezer in a secure location until instructions are received from the agency regarding the disposition of the specimen or until the agency takes custody of the specimen.
29. **Post-Construction Compliance Report.** Caltrans will submit a post-construction compliance report to the Sacramento Fish and Wildlife Office (SFO) within 60 calendar days following each year of construction or within 60 calendar days of any break in construction activity lasting more than 60 calendar days. This report will detail (i) dates that construction occurred; (ii) pertinent information concerning the success of the project in meeting compensation and other conservation measures; (iii) an explanation of failure to meet such measures, if any; (iv) known project effects on the California clapper rail or salt marsh harvest mouse, if any; (v) occurrences of incidental take; (vi) documentation of employee environmental education; and (vii) other pertinent information. The reports will be addressed to the Coast-Bay Branch Chief of the Endangered Species Program, SFO and the Environmental Compliance Specialist, Planning Division.
30. **Reinitiation of Consultation.** Caltrans will reinitiate consultation if it becomes apparent that the project may result in effects to listed species or their critical habitat that was not considered in this Biological Opinion.

31. **Service Access.** If requested, before, during, or upon completion of groundbreaking and construction activities, Caltrans will allow access by Service personnel into the project footprint to inspect the project and its activities.

Action Area

The action area is defined in 50 CFR § 402.02, as “all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action.” For the proposed project, the action area encompasses an 8.98-acre construction footprint (6.61 acres of existing hardscape + 2.19 acres of landscape + 0.13 acre of aquatic features + 0.05 acre of ice-plant vegetation) plus a 0.25 mile habitat buffer to account for noise, lighting, vibration, and visual disturbance.

Analytical Framework for the Jeopardy Determinations

Section 7(a)(2) of the Endangered Species Act requires that federal agencies ensure that any action they authorize, fund, or carry out is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species. “Jeopardize the continued existence of” means to engage in an action that reasonably would be expected, directly or indirectly, to reduce appreciably the likelihood of both the survival and recovery of a listed species in the wild by reducing the reproduction, numbers, or distribution of that species (50 CFR § 402.02).

The jeopardy analysis in this biological opinion considers the effects of the proposed federal action, and any cumulative effects, on the range wide survival and recovery of the listed species. It relies on four components: (1) the *Status of the Species*, which describes the range wide condition of the species, the factors responsible for that condition, and its survival and recovery needs; (2) the *Environmental Baseline*, which analyzes the condition of the species in the action area, the factors responsible for that condition, and the relationship of the action area to the survival and recovery of the species; (3) the *Effects of the Action*, which determines the direct and indirect impacts of the proposed federal action and the effects of any interrelated or interdependent activities on the species; and (4) the *Cumulative Effects*, which evaluates the effects of future, non-federal activities in the action area on the species.

Status of the Species

California Clapper Rail

For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the California clapper rail’s range-wide status, please refer to the species’ 2013 *5-Year Review* (Service 2013). No change in the species’ listing status was recommended in the review. The *5-Year Review* does not include the threat, recovery, survey data, and other relevant updates for the species since its issuance. Since that time, actions have been implemented that have resulted in additional adverse effects to the species. In association with those actions, conservation measures have been implemented for the purpose of minimizing those adverse effects and in some cases, restoring or enhancing California clapper rail habitat. While the threats posed by habitat loss, degradation, and fragmentation as well as other factors including loss of buffer zones, wastewater discharges, and human disturbance are ongoing, to date no project has proposed a level of effects for which the Service has issued a biological opinion of jeopardy for the species.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

The salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail share the same tidal marsh habitat and experience similar threats. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the salt marsh harvest mouse’s range-wide status, please refer to the species’ 2010 *5-Year Review* (Service 2010). No change in the species’ listing status was recommended in the review. The *5-Year Review* does not include the

threat, recovery, survey data, and other relevant updates for the species since its issuance. Since that time, actions have been implemented that have resulted in additional adverse effects to the species. In association with those actions, conservation measures have been implemented for the purpose of minimizing those adverse effects and in some cases, restoring or enhancing California clapper rail habitat. While the threats similar to those stated for the California clapper rail are ongoing, to date no project has proposed a level of effects for which the Service has issued a biological opinion of jeopardy for the species.

Environmental Baseline

The proposed project area is located within the East San Francisco Bay City of Richmond. Richmond is on the western edge of an urban and residential sprawl that fills the landscape from the San Pablo Ridge to the east, west to the edge of the Bay. Despite the long history of human development, native species continue to persist along the margins of the Bay. Tidal wetlands that were once expansive and rich in biological diversity and production, have been reduced to narrow outlines of habitat degraded by invasive plants and animals, water pollution, light, noise, and a host of other adverse factors. Species such as the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse are unique to these tidal zones and are therefore imperiled by these factors. However, these two species persist in low numbers when the available habitat continues to provide an adequate measure of the resources they need to complete their lifecycle.

The majority of the project footprint is within the Caltrans right-of-way (ROW). Further downstream, Baxter Creek runs adjacent to, and the Stege Marsh is partially contained within McLaughlin Eastshore State Park. Baxter meets the marsh near a former railroad berm that is now a recreational path, administered by the East Bay Regional Park District. The area experiences typical urban-associated influences such as congested and consistent traffic on I-580, noise, night-time lighting, feral animals, and recreation.

According to calculations in Caltrans' 2018 BA, the project footprint includes 0.09 acre of perennial stream, 0.03 acre of emergent wetland, 0.01 acre of engineered channel, 0.05 acre of ice plant mats, and 2.19 acres of ruderal annual grassland/landscaped. Pickleweed and other tidal wetland vegetation associated with the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse increases as the creek flows to the western end of the action area within the Stege Marsh.

Baxter Creek is a perennial drainage flowing west to the Stege Marsh and the San Francisco Bay. The creek passes through heavy development on its way downslope from the Berkeley Hills to the marsh. Its course has been significantly modified with the majority of its length confined to culverts as it has been routed under developed areas. As noted on the *Friends of Baxter Creek* website (<https://web.archive.org/web/20060902144233/http://www.creativedifferences.com:80/baxtercreek/index.html>), portions of the creek, primarily upstream of the proposed project area, have been subjected to riparian restoration efforts. The modified nature of the drainage is apparent at the I-580 crossing within the project area, where the creek closely parallels the Interstate before making a 90 degree turn to cross under the road. West of I-580, the creek follows a well-defined channel approximately 0.25 mile to the marsh. The Stege Marsh and the tidal influenced area extending up Baxter Creek continue to provide degraded, but suitable habitat for the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse.

The proposed footprint is located within the range of the salt marsh harvest mouse and the California clapper rail. A map depicting the endangered rail's range is included in the Service's online profile for the species at <https://ecos.fws.gov/ecp0/profile/speciesProfile?sId=4240>. The endangered mouse's range can be found at <https://ecos.fws.gov/ecp0/profile/speciesProfile?>

sId=613. Recovery roadmaps for both species are outlined in the Service's *Recovery Plan for the Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California* and the proposed action area, west of I-580, is within this plan's Central/South San Francisco Bay Recovery Unit (Service 2013).

The California Natural Diversity Database (CNDDDB) includes documented observations of both species along the tidal margins of the San Pablo and San Francisco Bays (CDFW 2018). These include records of the species in narrow bands of remaining habitat in close proximity to heavily traveled highways and urban areas. For example, the salt marsh harvest mouse occurs within the Caltrans ROW along the eastern approach to the I-80 Bay Bridge, approximately 5 miles south of the action area (CNDDDB salt marsh harvest mouse occurrence #102, CDFW 2018). The California clapper rail has been recorded approximately 0.2 mile from the project footprint within the Stege Marsh and in closer proximity to I-580 immediately adjacent to the southern extent of the proposed project footprint (CNDDDB California Ridgeway's rail occurrence #28, CDFW 2018).

The salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail habitat within the action area is influenced by the use of the I-580 transportation corridor and surrounding land use. The ROW includes several associated features such as vehicle pullouts, overhead utilities, road signs, and a road shoulder that is subject to vegetation maintenance. These physical features along with traffic volume, traffic noise, exhaust, fluid leaks, invasive vegetation, and the threat of animal-vehicle collision have an adverse effect on the function of the neighboring habitat for both common and listed wildlife. This parallel band of disturbance is referred to as a "road effects zone." The outward extent of this zone can vary with factors such as topography and the sensitivity of a given species to those effects. A spectrum of typical road effects are likely to negatively influence the suitability of the tidal marsh habitat in and adjacent to the project footprint as well as the behavior of the species within their respective road effects zone.

Although road mortality may be a risk for both species, their movement and dispersal is most likely oriented within the marshlands north, south, and west of I-580. The listed rail and mouse are more likely adversely affected by the other factors associated with roads and these baseline conditions likely create a risk that diminishes with distance from the roadway.

The Service believes that the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse are reasonably certain to occur within the action area due to: (1) the project footprint being located within the species' range and current distribution; (2) the presence of suitable tidal marsh habitat within the action area; (3) the California clapper rail has been previously documented in the action area and the salt marsh harvest mouse presence has been documented in nearby areas with similar habitat and conditions; (4) both species have the potential to occur in tidal wetlands that outline the margins of the San Francisco Bay; and (5) the biology and ecology of the animals.

Effects of the Action

The direct effects of the proposed project are those effects occurring within the action area during construction of the proposed project. The effects of habitat loss and disturbance were analyzed based on the term of the loss, restoration potential, and the associated changes to functional value. As a result, effects were characterized as permanent or temporary.

The proposed project footprint does not include the tidally-influenced pickleweed habitat closely associated with the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse. Habitat within the project footprint is limited to what would be considered upland ruderal areas where either species may retreat during high tide events or occasional foraging and dispersal attempts. Overall, both species typically remain within limits of the tidal marsh and are less likely to occupy the proposed project

footprint which is also subject to a higher level of baseline disturbance associated with I-580. Attempted efforts to move into the active work area will be discouraged by both the harassing nature of the activities and the installation of the WEF at the western bounds of the footprint. Therefore, the direct effects of the project are more likely to be associated with the noise, light, and visual disturbance associated with the proposed construction activities. These effects on individuals and the suitability of habitat within that action area will most likely be temporary.

Indirect effects are the effects of the proposed project generally occurring later in time after construction has been completed (*e.g.*, degradation of habitat due to the spread of invasive plant species; barriers to dispersal due to the installation of retaining walls). Potential indirect effects are often difficult to identify prior to the action or to quantify following the action. Indirect effects for the proposed project may include increased sediment load downstream should post-construction erosion control be ineffective. An interrelated activity is an activity that is part of the proposed project and depends on the proposed project for its justification. An interdependent activity is an activity that has no independent utility apart from the action under consultation. No other actions or proposed actions, other than those described in the project description, were identified as interrelated or interdependent activities.

Caltrans proposes to minimize project-related direct and indirect effects by implementing the *Conservation Measures* included in the project description section of this Biological Opinion. Effective implementation of *Conservation Measures* will likely minimize effects to the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse during construction but incidental take is still likely to occur. Therefore, we expect the proposed project to result in a variety of adverse effects to the listed rail and mouse.

The noise, vibration, nighttime lighting, and activity associated with the construction will be disruptive and may result in the impairment of essential California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse behavior patterns.

California clapper rails tend to be most active and vocal at dusk and dawn; low light periods that will be compromised by both artificial lighting and elevated noise levels. Although the rail may be acclimated to the baseline noise, the incremental increase will be paired with the visual disturbance of workers and equipment. Increased noise levels can hamper the ability of the California clapper rail to effectively broadcast its calls and detect the calls of other clapper rails. Caltrans will minimize the disruption of breeding behavior with a restrictive seasonal work window. However, excessive noise will hinder their ability to maintain territories within the active work window. Noise and light may also deter the dispersal of juvenile and adult rails following the breeding season. Disruption may also encumber the bird's ability to detect and avoid predators such as domestic cats.

Increased noise and artificial light could affect the ability of the California clapper rail and the salt marsh harvest mouse to forage and increase their detection by predators. This may be exacerbated during evening high tide events when both species would venture closer to the project footprint.

Limiting construction activities to between July 15 and January 31 should be effective in avoiding the disturbance of nesting California clapper rails which may have resulted in egg loss, injury to nestlings, or nest abandonment. Restrictive use and shielding of night lighting will likely minimize illumination of nearby habitat and disruption of rail and mouse behaviors. Avoidance of working during the identified extreme high tides will minimize disturbance to salt marsh harvest mice as they may be forced to move closer to the project footprint in search of refuge. Covering and inspecting steep-walled excavations prior to filling will avoid the inadvertent entombment of a salt marsh harvest mouse.

Educating project personnel will encourage compliance with the conservation measures and increase the possibility that California clapper rails and salt marsh harvest mice in the work area will be identified and addressed appropriately for avoidance. Worker education is limited by the effectiveness of the presentation and the willingness of the construction personnel to participate in compliance.

Pre-construction surveys by an Agency-Approved Biological Monitor will assist in identifying California clapper rails and salt marsh harvest mice or their sign in the work areas prior to the introduction of a potential construction-related threat. Biological clearance of work areas is limited by the experience of the biologist the inconspicuous nature of the species, and the challenges of completing a thorough clearance given the construction schedule. The California clapper rail is primarily detected by call. The species is known to have a loud call but detectability diminishes with background noise. Therefore it will be relatively difficult for the rails to be identified with given the baseline highway-related noise with the elevated noise levels due to construction. The species is secretive, calls are not broadcast throughout the year, or reliably.

The installation of a WEF at the western boundary of the project will be useful in discouraging salt marsh harvest mice from entering active work areas and as an identifying feature of the project limits. The effectiveness of the fence will depend on proper installation and maintenance.

California clapper rails, salt marsh harvest mice, and their food items could be harmed by contamination due to chemical or sediment discharge. Exposure pathways could include inhalation, dermal contact, direct ingestion, or secondary ingestion of contaminated soil, plants or food. Exposure to contaminants could cause short- or long-term morbidity, possibly resulting in reduced productivity or mortality. However, Caltrans proposes to reduce these risks by implementing BMPs and the SWMP that consist of refueling, oiling, or cleaning of vehicles and equipment a minimum of 50 feet from riparian and aquatic areas; installing coir rolls, straw wattles and/or silt fencing to capture sediment and prevent runoff or other harmful chemicals from entering the aquatic habitat; and locating staging, storage and parking areas away from aquatic habitat.

Caltrans' commitment to use erosion control devices other than mono-filament should be effective in avoiding the associated risk of entrapment that can result in death by predation, starvation, or desiccation (Stuart *et al.* 2001).

The completed project is unlikely to increase the local risk of clapper rail or harvest mouse mortality from vehicle collision. The in-kind bridge replacement is not likely to result in significant increases in traffic volume or speed. The completed project will not provide greater access to the roadway or result in the addition of structures such as barriers that may result in greater risk of being stranded in the roadway increasing their risk of being killed. Likewise, the road effects zone described in the baseline section is unlikely to expand.

Ice plant is a notable invasive non-native plant that can replace native vegetation communities and dominate coastal habitats. Its removal from the work area may be helpful in limiting its future spread in the action area.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the action area considered in this Biological Opinion. Future federal actions that are unrelated to the I-580 Stege Drain Bridge Rehabilitation Project are not considered in this section because they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. During

this consultation, the Service did not identify any future non-federal actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the action area of the proposed project.

Conclusion

After reviewing the current status of the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse, the environmental baseline for the action area, the effects of the proposed I-580 Stege Drain Bridge Rehabilitation Project, and the cumulative effects, it is the Service's biological opinion that the I-580 Stege Drain Bridge Rehabilitation Project, as proposed, is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the California clapper rail or salt marsh harvest mouse. The Service reached this conclusion because the project-related effects to the species, when added to the environmental baseline and analyzed in consideration of all potential cumulative effects, will not rise to the level of precluding recovery or reducing the likelihood of survival of the species based on the following: (1) successful implementation of the described *Conservation Measures* is likely to reduce the potential for proposed project activities to result in the disruption of normal California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest behavior and avoid risk of injury; (2) ground-disturbing activities will be limited to ruderal upland habitat beyond the species' primary pickleweed-centered habitat; (3) adverse effects are likely limited to disturbance; (4) the ground disturbing activities will be located within and adjacent to the existing roadway alignment, and (5) the project is limited to an in-kind replacement of existing infrastructure.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and Federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as to harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harass is defined by Service regulations at 50 CFR 17.3 as an intentional or negligent act or omission which creates the likelihood of injury to wildlife by annoying it to such an extent as to significantly disrupt normal behavior patterns which include, but are not limited to, breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Harm is defined by the same regulations as an act which actually kills or injures wildlife. Harm is further defined to include significant habitat modification or degradation that results in death or injury to listed species by significantly impairing essential behavior patterns, including breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Incidental take is defined as take that is incidental to, and not the purpose of, the carrying out of an otherwise lawful activity. Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking that is incidental to and not intended as part of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act provided that such taking is in compliance with the terms and conditions of this *Incidental Take Statement*.

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be undertaken by the Caltrans so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the applicant, as appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. The Caltrans has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If the Caltrans (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions or (2) fails to require the applicant to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, Caltrans must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR §402.14(i)(3)].

Amount or Extent of Take

California Clapper Rail

The Service anticipates that incidental take of the California clapper rail will be difficult to detect because the species is secretive and conspicuous, injured birds may travel outside the observational range of the Agency-Approved Biological Monitor, and some forms of harm may not be apparent until after construction is complete. Losses of this species may also be difficult to quantify due to a lack of baseline survey data and seasonal/annual fluctuations in their numbers due to environmental or human-caused disturbances. Harm will be difficult to detect and measure for similar reasons. There is a risk of non-lethal harm as a result of the noise, vibration, and light disturbance as well as the equipment and human presence associated with the proposed construction activities. Therefore, the Service is authorizing take incidental to the proposed action as the non-lethal harm of all California clapper rails within the areas action area. No take is issued related to mortality.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

The Service anticipates that incidental take of the salt marsh harvest mouse will be difficult to detect because the species is small, inconspicuous within the vegetation that it occupies, is found in a consistently fluctuating tidal environment, injured mice may travel outside the observational range of the Agency-Approved Biological Monitor, and some forms of harm may not be apparent until after construction is complete. Losses of this species may also be difficult to quantify due to a lack of baseline survey data and seasonal/annual fluctuations in their numbers due to environmental or human-caused disturbances. Harm will be difficult to detect and measure for similar reasons. There is a risk of non-lethal harm as a result of the noise, vibration, and light disturbance as well as the equipment and human presence associated with the proposed construction activities. Therefore, the Service is authorizing take incidental to the proposed action as the non-lethal harm of all salt marsh harvest mice within the proposed action area. No take is issued related to mortality.

Upon implementation of the following *Reasonable and Prudent Measures*, the incidental take of the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse associated with the proposed project in proportion to the amount and type of take outlined above will become exempt from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act. No other forms of take are exempted under this opinion.

Effect of the Take

In the accompanying biological opinion, the Service determined that this level of anticipated take for the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse is not likely to result in jeopardy to either species.

Reasonable and Prudent Measure

The Service has determined that the following reasonable and prudent measure is necessary and appropriate to minimize the effect of the action on the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse. Caltrans will be responsible for the implementation and compliance with this measure:

1. Minimize the adverse effects to the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse and their habitat in the action area by implementing the proposed project, including the *Conservation Measures* as described, with the following *Terms and Conditions*.

Terms and Conditions

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, Caltrans must ensure compliance with the following terms and conditions, which implement the reasonable and prudent measure described above. These terms and conditions are nondiscretionary.

1. The following *Terms and Conditions* implement *Reasonable and Prudent Measure* one (1):
 - a. Caltrans shall include a copy of all relevant permits within the construction bid package of the proposed project. The Resident Engineer or their designee shall be responsible for implementing the *Conservation Measures* and *Terms and Conditions* of the Biological Opinion.
 - b. Approval request for Agency-Approved Biological Monitors shall include, at a minimum: (1) relevant education; (2) relevant training concerning California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse identification, survey techniques, handling individuals of different age classes, and handling of different life stages by a permitted biologist or recognized species expert authorized for such activities by the Service; (3) a summary of field experience conducting requested activities (to include project/research information); (4) a summary of Biological Opinions under which they were authorized to work with the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse and at what level (such as construction monitoring versus handling), this will also include the names and qualifications of persons under which the work was supervised as well as the amount of work experience on the actual project; (5) a list of Federal Recovery Permits [10(a)1(A)] held or under which they are authorized to work with the species (to include permit number, authorized activities, and name of permit holder); and (6) any relevant professional references with contact information. No project construction will begin until Caltrans has received written Service approval for biologists to conduct specified activities.

Reporting Requirements

In order to monitor whether the amount or extent of incidental take anticipated from implementation of the project is approached or exceeded, Caltrans shall adhere to the following reporting requirements. Should this anticipated amount or extent of incidental take be exceeded, Caltrans must reinitiate formal consultation as per 50 CFR 402.16.

1. Notification of injured or dead listed species will be made to the Coast-Bay Division Chief of the Endangered Species Program at the SFO at (916) 414-6623. When an injured or dead individual of the listed species is found, Caltrans shall follow the steps outlined in the following *Disposition of Individuals Taken* section.
2. Sightings of any listed or sensitive animal species should be reported to the CNDDDB (<http://www.dfg.ca.gov/biogeodata/cnddb/>).
3. Construction compliance reports will be addressed to the Coast-Bay Division Chief of the Endangered Species Program at the SFO.
4. Caltrans shall submit post-construction compliance reports prepared by the Agency-Approved Biological Monitor to the Service within 60 calendar days following completion of each construction season or within 60 calendar days of any break in construction activity lasting more than 60 calendar days. This report shall detail (1) dates that relevant project activities occurred; (2) pertinent information concerning the success of the project in

implementing avoidance and minimization measures; (3) an explanation of failure to meet such measures, if any; (4) known project effects on the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse; (5) occurrences of incidental take of any listed species; (6) documentation of employee environmental education; and (7) other pertinent information.

CONSERVATION RECOMMENDATIONS

Section 7(a)(1) of the Act directs federal agencies to utilize their authorities to further the purposes of the Act by carrying out conservation programs for the benefit of endangered and threatened species. Conservation recommendations are discretionary agency activities to minimize or avoid adverse effects of a proposed action on listed species or critical habitat, to help implement recovery plans, or to develop information. The Service recommends the following actions:

1. Caltrans District 4 should work with the Service to develop a conservation strategy that would identify the current safe passage potential along Bay Area highways and the areas where safe passage for wildlife could be enhanced or established.
2. Caltrans should assist the Service in implementing recovery actions identified in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California* (Service 2013).
3. Caltrans should consider participating in the planning for a regional habitat conservation plan for the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse, other listed species, and at-risk species.
4. Caltrans should consider establishing functioning preservation and creation conservation banking systems to further the conservation of the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse. Such banking systems also could be utilized for other required mitigation (i.e., seasonal wetlands, riparian habitats, etc.) where appropriate. Efforts should be made to preserve habitat along roadways in association with wildlife crossings.
5. Caltrans should ensure that their container plants used for restoration are sourced from nurseries utilizing the Working Group for Phytophthoras in Native Habitats' *Guidelines to Minimize Phytophthora Pathogens in Restoration Nurseries* (available at http://www.suddenoakdeath.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/04/Restoration.Nsy_Guidelines.final_.092216.pdf).

In order for the Service to be kept informed of actions minimizing or avoiding adverse effects or benefiting listed species or their habitats, the Service requests notification of the implementation of any conservation recommendations.

REINITIATION--CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes formal consultation on the I-580 Stege Drain Bridge Rehabilitation Project. As provided in 50 CFR §402.16, reinitiation of formal consultation is required and shall be requested by the federal agency or by the Service where discretionary federal agency involvement or control over the action has been retained or is authorized by law and: (a) if the amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded; (b) if new information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered; (c) if the identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion; or (d) if a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.

If you have questions concerning this consultation or implementation of its measures, please contact John Cleckler, Caltrans Liaison (john_cleckler@fws.gov), or at (916) 414-6639 or Ryan Olah, Coast-Bay Division Chief, (ryan_olah@fws.gov), at (916) 414-6623, or the letterhead address.

Sincerely,

Jennifer M. Norris, Ph.D.
Field Supervisor

cc:

Robert Stanley, California Department of Fish and Wildlife, Napa, California
John Yeakel and Denis Coghlan Caltrans District 4, Oakland, California
Kim Squires, Bay Delta Fish & Wildlife Office, Sacramento, California

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